

Wondering How You Can Safely Move Gym Equipment? Check Out This

Moving is not a load but the things you wanna move are, because if anything happens to your possession during the move you can't settle easily and when it comes to tough moving goods gym equipment falls in it whether it is as simple as yoga mat or as complicated as treadmill, you have to put a care on how to move them safely without hurting them as well as the property. There is right as well as wrong way to move your gym partners and today [Packers and Movers in Kolkata](#) will tell you how you can ace it and have a successful move.

First comes first: cleaning and sanitizing:

Cleaning and sanitizing your gym equipment properly is the first thing you have to do while preparing them for a move, this way you can save yourself and your new home from any nasty bacteria and germ for entering in your new home, also cleaning will keep your equipment in #top on looks after the #move.

Packers and Movers in Kolkata suggest.

1. Wipe down your yoga mate and yoga accessories using paper towels and all purpose cleaner or all natural spray, if you don't wanna try them you can buy a specific cleaner for cleaning your yoga mat.
2. Thoroughly clean all handrails on the treadmill, weight machine, elliptical and on other workout machine. To clean your gear I suggest you should go for wet wipes or your homemade solution for that mix 50/50 ratio water and vinegar and spray to your equipment.
3. Wash towels and blankets on a hot water cycle.

Second: How to move?

For hand weights, barbells and dumbbells

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Whether you own multiple set of weight plates or few light hand weights it's important to make sure your moving box can handle them successfully. For heavy weight goods we recommend to use smaller boxes rather than stuffing all in one which that will not only make the box really heavy and can also increase the chances of dropping as well as tearing. If you think your cardboard boxes are not that sturdy then it's better to buy or look in your house what can hold them like bag or plastic bin. Get Packing and Moving help from professionals like *Local Packers and Movers in Kolkata* and leave your worry for a good.

Decided on the boxes now when you pack them wrap them in bubble wrap or newspaper so they won't rub against each other and create a scratch or damage the box you can also fill any vacant space with the newspaper balls or old cloths, blankets or towels.

For treadmill.

Moving large equipment is exercise in itself, but using the right technique you can make it less daunting. Thoroughly wipe and unplug your treadmill, make sure all wires are disconnected from the walls. When you are going for lifting find a few helpers and fold and lock it into a place in upright position. Once folded then wrap your treadmill in #moving blanket to avoid any damage.

Treadmills are heavy so for moving it to the moving truck we recommend you get some moving dolly or hand trucks having wheels to make the work the easy, also while lifting it on hand truck or any other moving equipment make sure you know the moving techniques of lifting like don't put any pressure on back lift with your legs, for more details check out **#Packers and #Movers guide**. Now carefully roll it forward make sure the way is clear and with the help of assistant hoist it up on moving truck.

For elliptical.

Elliptical can be tricky to move than treadmill due to its bulky shape. Using wrench and screw driver disassemble the elliptical pedals and handlebars, and make sure to keep the screw and bolts in clear and labelled zip lock or any bag. Once it's disassembled it will become light weight and easy to handle, still don't forget to cover it up in moving blanket. Before disassembling make sure you know the steps.

For stationary bike.

People are preferring to have spin at home rather than going out due to many reasons like pollution traffic and suitability of time, thankfully moving them is also that much flexible. If you have electric bike make sure to unplug all the plugs and secure them in one place. Before you move your bike make sure to place something underneath the bicycle to avoid any scratches. Once you gotten the bike to truck with the help of two or three people lift it on the truck, also cover it in moving blanket so to avoid any dust.

For yoga mat.

#Pack your yoga accessories like yoga blocks, towels and gym blankets in a box sturdy enough to handle them till the move is complete. Now roll your yoga mat and secure it with carrying strap to save the space. Also if you can find any box in which it can fit its good but don't forget to cover it up in moving blanket and secure it with strap.

Your friends are not available on the moving day, don't worry get your assistance from [Movers and Packers in Hooghly](#) and make your move safe and sound.

Packers And Movers Kolkata to Lucknow

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